

Cyclocondensation and Cycloaddition Reactions on the Unsaturated Centre of Arylidene-2-aminobenzoxazole

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Arylidene-2-aminobenzoxazoles (III) were prepared by the condensation of 2-aminobenzoxazole with aromatic aldehydes. Cyclocondensation of mercaptoacetic acid, chloroacetyl chloride and diazoalkanes on III, give the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones (IV), azetidinones (V) and triazolines (VI) respectively. The biological activities of the prepared compounds were screened against some bacteria and fungi.

BENZOXAZOLE derivatives are reported to possess anti-inflammatory¹, antiseptic², food and feed preservation² and antimicrobial detergent^{3,4} properties. It was of interest to incorporate benzoxazole molecule into the well known antimicrobial nuclei thiazolidinone, azetidinone and triazolines and to evaluate their biological activities. On this basis, synthesis and structural elucidation of some new benzoxazolothiazolidinones, benzoxazoloazetidinones and benzoxazolo-triazolines were undertaken.

2-Aminobenzoxazole was reported⁵ to be formed through direct interaction of hydroxylamine with benzoxazole in alkaline medium. However, when we tried its synthesis, a preliminary intermediate crystalline product, 2-hydroxylamino-2,3-dihydrobenzoxazole (I), was obtained. It was transformed into the corresponding 2-aminobenzoxazole (II) when boiled in 10% NaOH solution or on heating at 180-200° for 5 min.

The structure of the intermediate compound I was confirmed by its ir spectrum which showed two stretching vibration bands at 3300 cm⁻¹ and 3150 cm⁻¹ characteristic of NH—OH association, a band at 1250 cm⁻¹ of C—N and a strong absorption band at 1100 cm⁻¹ of C—O—C⁶. Its nmr spectrum was characterised by $\delta = 6.9$ (4 H, s, aromatic) and $\delta = 7.3$ (1 H, m, —CH).

Condensation of 2-aminobenzoxazole (II) with aromatic aldehydes in ethanol solution and piperidine gave the corresponding products, arylidene-2-aminobenzoxazoles (III).

The structure of compounds III has been established from their analytical data (cf. Table 1). The ir spectra showed absorption bands at 1640-1605, 1605-1590 and 1560-1545 cm⁻¹ for the oxazole system⁷ and band at 1670-1640 cm⁻¹ for C=N group.

The interaction of mercaptoacetic acid with compounds IIIa, b, d, e, f and i in dry benzene produced cycloaddition products, 3-(2-benzoxazolyl)-4-thiazolidinones (IV) (cf. Table 1). In the

ir spectra, the stretching vibration band characteristic of the >C=O group⁸ was observed at 1700-1695 cm⁻¹.

β -Lactam ring structure is known⁹ to be the part of the molecules responsible for the antibiotic activity of penicillin and cephalosporine C. Cycloaddition of IIIa, b, e and g with monochloroketene (prepared *in situ* from chloroacetylchloride and triethylamine) in dry benzene gave rise to 1-(2-benzoxazolyl)-2-azetidinones (V). The ir spectra of compounds V showed stretching vibration bands characteristic of the >C=O group (of monocyclic β -lactam structure^{6,10}), observed at 1705-1700 cm⁻¹.

Diazoalkanes were recorded¹¹⁻¹³ to condense with Schiff bases to give the corresponding cycloaddition products.

Arylidene-2-aminobenzoxazoles (IIIa-g) were treated with diazoalkanes (methane, ethane, propane and butane) in dry ether at -5° for 15 days. The compounds IIIb, c and g reacted successfully with diazomethane and ethane producing the corresponding 1,2,3-triazolines (VI). However, the compounds IIIa, b, e and f were recovered unreacted from the reaction mixture. The ir spectra of VI showed stretching vibration band at 1660 cm⁻¹ characteristic of -N=N- group and an absorption band at 1240-1245 cm⁻¹ characteristic of C—N group⁸.

Antibacterial and antifungal activities: Compounds of type III, IV and VI were tested *in vitro* for their biological activities on a variety of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria¹⁴ such as *S. aureus*, *P. pyocyanea*, *Proteus*, *E. coli* and *Serratia* and the fungi¹⁵ *A. niger*, *A. flavus* and *P. notatum*.

The results showed that most of the prepared compounds III, IV, V and VI possessed from a little to strong activities against the tested bacteria and fungi. The activity ranging from 36 to 75% inhibition was found at a concentration 10⁻⁸M. The strongly active compounds against *S. aureus* were

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| <p>VI; <u>R</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a: <i>m</i>-NO₂ b: <i>m</i>-NO₂ c: <i>p</i>-NO₂ d: <i>p</i>-NO₂ e: <i>p</i>-Cl f: <i>p</i>-Cl | <p><u>R'</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> H CH₃ H CH₃ H CH₃ |
|--|--|

IIIa, b, g and i; IVb, d, f and e), against *P. pyocyanea*, *Proteus* and *E. coli* were IIIb, g and i; IV b, e and f; Vb, e, g and VIe and f, against *Serratia* were IIIb, c; IVb and d; Vb and e and VIf and against *A. niger*, *A. flavus* and *P. notatum* were IIIa, d, g and i; IVb and e; Vb and g and VIc and d, respectively.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 200 G spectrophotometer. The uv spectra in spec. pure ethanol were taken on a Pye-Unicam SP 8000 Ultraviolet spectrophotometer. Silica gel "chromatographic grade" was used for preparing chromatoplates. NMR spectra in trifluoroacetic acid were recorded on a Varian, 60 MHz.

2-Aminobenzoxazole⁶ and 2-hydroxylamino-2,3-dihydrobenzoxazole (I): A mixture of benzoxazole (3.54 g), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2.1 g) and sodium hydroxide (45 ml; 1 N) was stirred for 3-4 hr on a water bath. The reaction mixture was cooled, whereby the crude 2-aminobenzoxazole was precipitated. This was filtered and recrystallized from benzene or water, m.p. 129-30°.

When the above procedure was carried out in lower concentration of NaOH (35 ml; 1 N), the precipitate recrystallized from benzene or water into compound I, m.p. 110° (mixed m.p. with 2-aminobenzoxazole 82°). It was easily soluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid, slightly soluble in

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS III, IV AND V

Compound* No.	R	m.p. °C	Solvent of:cryst.	Yield %	λ _{max} nm	ε value	IR cm ⁻¹
III, a	H	175	Pet. ether	60	290	2200	1660
	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	267	Benzene	70	385	2000	C=N 1642
	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	230	Benzene	57	—	—	C=N 1645
	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	174	Benzene	55	290	2400	1645
	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	230	Pet. ether	65	305	1500	C=N 1668
	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	135	Benzene	50	410	60000	C=N 1668
	<i>p</i> -Cl	182	Pet. ether	55	430	64000	C=N 1658
	<i>p</i> -OH	210	Toluene	58	—	—	C=N 1665
	<i>o</i> -OH	185	Benzene	55	290	2800	C=N 1665
IV, a	H	130	Benzene	40	345	9600	1709
	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	100	Benzene	60	—	—	C=O 1695
	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	150	Benzene	50	—	—	C=O 1700
	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	178	Benzene	55	—	—	C=O 1705
	<i>o</i> -OH	160	Chloroform	45	—	—	C=O 1702
	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	145	Chloroform	40	—	—	C=O 1700

(Table 1 Contd.)

V, a	H	210	Ethanol	32	—	—	1705 C=O
b	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	190	Ethanol	35	—	—	1702 C=O
e	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	256	Benzene	45	—	—	1700 C=O
g	<i>p</i> -Cl	140	Ethanol	30	—	—	1702 C=O

* Satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS VI

Compound* No. (VI)	R	R'	m.p. °C	Solvent of cryst.	Yield %	(IR): $\nu_{\text{cm}^{-1}}$	
						N=N	C-N
a	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	H	205	Dil. acetic	58	1660	1245
b	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	CH ₃	293	Benzene	50	1658	1240
c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	N	150	Ethanol + pet. ether	75	1660	1240
d	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	CH ₃	298	Ethanol + benzene	70	1658	1242
e	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	306	Benzene	50	1658	1240
f	<i>p</i> -Cl	CH ₃	275	Benzene	52	1657	1240

* Satisfactory C, H and N analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

cold NaOH solution and gave no violet colour with FeCl₃ (Found: C, 55.10; H, 4.97; N, 18.30. Calcd.: C, 55.26; H, 5.26; N, 18.42%).

Effect of heat on 2-hydroxylamino-2,3-dihydrobenzoxazole (I): A dry sample of I (1 g) was heated on oil bath for 5 min at 180-200°, the melt was cooled to room temperature and crystallized from benzene, mixed m.p. with 2-aminobenzoxazole from benzene, mixed m.p. with 2-aminobenzoxazole was unchanged (129-30°). The product showed the same ir spectrum and tlc analysis (R_f 0.81 benzene : *n*-hexane = 3 : 1) as of 2-aminobenzoxazole.

Effect of 10% NaOH on 2-hydroxylamino-2,3-dihydrobenzoxazole (I): A mixture of I (1 g) and 10% sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml) was boiled for 10 min and cooled. The precipitate was filtered, dried and crystallized from benzene. Its m.p. and mixed m.p. with 2-aminobenzoxazole was unchanged. It showed superimposable ir spectrum and identical tlc analysis with an authentic sample.

Arylidene-2-aminobenzoxazoles (III): Equimolecular amounts (0.01 mole) of the aldehyde and 2-aminobenzoxazole was refluxed in dry alcohol (15 ml) in presence of a few drops of piperidine for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was concentrated and cooled. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallized from proper solvent (Table 1).

Substituted 3-(2-benzoxazolyl)-4-thiazolidinones (IV): A mixture of Schiff base III a, b, e, f and i (0.02 mole) and of mercaptoacetic acid (0.02 mole) in 100 ml dry benzene was refluxed with a water separator until the theoretical amount of water had been collected. Excess benzene was evaporated, the residue washed with a 1 : 1 mixture of benzene-petroleum ether (40-60) several times, dissolved in ether and seeded. The product so obtained was recrystallized from proper solvent (Table 1).

Substituted 1-(2-benzoxazolyl)-2-azetidiones (V): To a mixture of Schiff bases III a, b, e and g (0.01 mole) and NEt₃ (0.02 mole) in dry benzene (40 ml) was added monochloroacetyl chloride (0.02 mole) dropwise at room temperature. The mixture was stirred for 5 hr and kept at room temperature for 5 days. The precipitate formed (triethylamine hydrochloride) was filtered, washed with the same solvent. The combined solvent and the filtrate was washed with dil. HCl and water and dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. After filtration the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was collected and crystallized from proper solvent (Table 1).

1,2,3-Triazolines (VI): Etheral solutions of the Schiff base III a, b, c, d, e, f and g (1 g) was treated with excess of cold etheral diazoalkanes (diazomethane, diazoethane, diazopropane and/or diazobutane). The reaction mixture was kept at -5° for 15 days, during which fresh amounts of etheral diazoalkane solution were added after 5 days. The ether was then evaporated and in every case the product was filtered, washed with light petroleum ether (40-60) and crystallized from the proper solvent (Table 1). For the Schiff bases having *p*-N(CH₃)₂, *p*-OCH₃ and *o*-nitro group in the arylidene moiety, the starting compounds were recovered unchanged. For diazopropane and diazobutane no reaction took place with the Schiff bases used. The results are listed in Table 2.

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